

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MAKING MADMPS WORK FOR YOU

A GUIDE FOR RESEARCHERS

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bit.ly/mappilot

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If you're a researcher, you're likely overwhelmed with demands on your time and inundated with funder and institutional policy requirements and suggestions that compete for your attention. While some find completing Data Management Plans (DMPs) a useful aspect of their teams' research management, others may regard them as just another item on the to-do list to disregard after the grant application has been submitted.

Benefits of maDMPs to you

01. Enhanced data organization and management

maDMPs can help researchers like you plan how to collect, store, and manage data throughout the research lifecycle, ensuring data is well-organized and easily accessible. They can facilitate the preparation of data for archiving and future use, enabling further research after the project has ended. These plans can also help identify the resources needed to support projects, such as storage space and software. Integrations can trigger notifications to supporting departments, including IT and Information Security, the Office of Sponsored Projects and Grant Offices, and Data Librarians, automatically informing them of the required resources and ensuring you get what you need to conduct your research.

02. Compliance with funding requirements

Most funding agencies, including NSF and NIH, require submission of DMPs as part of their grant proposals, ensuring that research data is managed according to their policies. Some require DMPs to be machine-readable. maDMPs help meet federal, funder and, in some cases, institutional requirements for data sharing, accessibility, and preservation, by bringing in guidance and policy information to the researcher while they are drafting the DMP. The DMP Tool brings in guidance from both the funder and your institution so you can see what you need to follow while drafting your plan.

03. Improved data sharing and reusability

DMPs encourage deeper consideration of how to share data with others, promoting collaboration and accelerating scientific discovery. By documenting data management practices, DMPs facilitate easier understanding, access, and reuse of data, ultimately leading to more impactful research. When using a tool such as the DMP Tool, maDMPs connect related research outputs to the DMP, facilitating the reliable discovery of related data. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of data and article citation. When other researchers generate maDMPs, it can also lead to your own data discovery and re-use, augmenting your research.

04. Flexibility to update your plan

maDMPs can be updated over time, reflecting changes in a plan, making it easier to fill out funder or institutionally-required progress reports on data management. Rather than relying on a static word document that can be hard to find and share, using a service like DMP Tool makes it easy to keep your DMPs in one place across devices and institutions, and collaborate with others online. Over time, you can update your DMP in the tool if your plan changes as your research progresses so you always have one source of truth about data management.

05. Time-savings and cost-effectiveness

maDMPs can save time and resources by preventing data loss, duplication, and unnecessary effort, especially when integrated with other systems. They can help you make informed decisions about data management early in the research process, avoiding potential problems later on. Institutions are working to implement integrations and tools that have the potential to reduce data entry, such as pulling in contributor or project information automatically, to save you time. Forthcoming AI tools for reviewing and drafting DMPs may offer help in creating high-quality DMPs more quickly.

Recommendations

Use persistent identifiers

PIDs (for the DMP, datasets, researchers, funders, institutions, etc.) are a key component of maDMPs and enable connections between your work and related research outputs and help ensure you get credit for your research and good data stewardship. When you link your ORCID to your DMP Tool account and publish your DMP, that DMP goes into your ORCID profile as a citable piece of scholarly work. You should also cite your DMP in any papers or datasets that come from that project, keeping all your works connected in the scholarly ecosystem. Deposit your dataset in a repository that assigns a persistent identifier (e.g. Dryad, Zenodo.), helping all your work be connected and ensuring you get scholarly credit for it all.

Let maDMPs work for you

There are increasing examples of how institutions are planning to save researchers time by providing them with better and more consistent

support throughout the research workflow, thanks to the integration of maDMPs into their systems. For example, when you draft your DMP in the DMP Tool, you can submit your DMP directly to your institution's librarians for expert feedback, if they're a participating organization. This helps ensure your DMP is complete and compliant before you submit it to the funder.

Make sure that maDMP integrations work for you and your team

Get involved with teams exploring integrations at your institution by sharing your needs, identifying your funding and security requirements, consultation and IT needs, and resource-intensive and administrative parts of the research process. As API connections are developed, maDMPs will start to take less time. For example, your institution may eventually be able to build integrations that pull in information about your project into the maDMP so you don't have to enter it again, and it will be important for the groups developing that on campus to know where you keep that information and what connections to build.

Don't abandon your DMP once submitted to a funder

maDMPs are living documents. Funders are often now asking for progress reports on your data management, not just scientific processes. Updating your DMP helps make these reports easy to fill out. They can also be used as a research management tool, and is also more useful to other departments (e.g., Information security, information technology, grants, the library, administration, etc.) in their work and resource provisioning when it contains current information, leading to more reliable support for your research. The more complete and accurate information you include in your DMP (such as what type of data you plan to collect and where you plan to store your data), the better the maDMP can integrate across systems, reducing your need for information re-entry and identifying related works.

Make your maDMP open if you can

If you register your DMP for a DMP ID, it can become a citable piece of work for your scholarly profile. As you add related works to it, such as datasets and papers that came from this project, it will be easier for people to find and cite your work, and to re-use data that you make available. You can choose to register the entire plan, or just the metadata.

Questions?

Find out more about maDMPs by visiting bit.ly/mappilot and viewing the resources created from the maDMPs Pilot. You can also ask your library about your institution's research data policies and planned or existing integrations using maDMPs.